

Non-Faradaic Electrolysis : Main Features*

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Manuscript received 22 February 1974; accepted 19 April 1974

FARADAY'S law is generally considered to be an inviolable truth. It is a marvel of simplicity as it merely states a one-to-one correspondence between the number of electrons entering or leaving a system and the number of equivalent species chemically changing at their zone of entry (viz. the cathode) and the zone of exit (viz. the anode). Of course, there are obvious exceptions, though not so well-known to physical chemists. One such exception is glow electrolysis, where current conduction is accompanied by glow at one of the electrodes—a phenomenon which is easily produced in the laboratory during electrolysis using D.C. mains.¹ The chemical decomposition is known to be as high as several hundred percent of that given by Faraday's law¹ and the gas liberated at the glowing electrode is found to be an explosive mixture of hydrogen and oxygen.² This led the speaker to investigate if such aberrations occur also during ordinary electrolysis but under somewhat high voltage and of course, without any glow.

cell containing 1(N) K_2SO_4 solution, the latter cell acting as the coulometer¹⁰. The electrolysis was allowed to run for months (well over a year) at a stretch, the gases collecting at the cathode and the anode being removed from time to time as soon as the gas burette at the cathode became nearly full. Water being the electrolyte, the current was naturally quite low, say, in the range of 0.3 mA to about one milliampere. It was immediately apparent that the behaviour of the water cell was highly anomalous³. The rate of production of gas in the water cell was very much less than that in the 1(N) K_2SO_4 cell in series as could be convincingly established from the fact that the gas burettes of the former had to be emptied less frequently than those of the latter. Besides, in the water-cell the ratio V_C/V_A was consistently greater than 2 and the most surprising observation was made that the cathode gas as well as the anode gas was a liberal mixture of hydrogen and oxygen. Some results are shown in Fig 2 and Table I

Fig. 1. Some typical electrolysis cells.

Electrolysis of water and the three Basic Anomalies

In the initial experiments, water was used as the electrolyte. A cell (some typical designs are shown in Fig. 1) was connected in series with an identical

The work was extended to other electrolytes and it was found that development of such anomalies is a general phenomenon with practically all electrolytes provided the current density and/or concentration are low (see next Section)⁴. So these anomalies may be considered a basic behaviour under the above conditions. These basic anomalies can be more clearly formulated^{3,4} as follows

Adapted from a lecture delivered by Prof. Santi R. Palit on December 27, 1973 during the Golden Jubilee celebration of the Indian Chemical Society.

Fig. 2. Results of electrolysis of conductivity water at varying current densities.

1) *First Anomaly : Volume Deficit*

V_C is less than V_{FC} and V_A is less than V_{FA} , where V_C and V_A are the actual volumes of gas liberated at cathode and anode respectively and V_{FC} and V_{FA} are the corresponding Faraday law values.

2) *Second Anomaly : Ratio Anomaly*

V_C/V_A is greater than 2. Under some conditions V_A tends to a very small value.

3) *Third Anomaly : Co-liberation*

V_C as well as V_A is an explosive mixture of hydrogen and oxygen, i.e. a liberal mixture of H_2 and O_2 is liberated at each of the electrodes.

Electrolysis of other Electrolytes

The anomalies occur not only with water but also with almost all electrolytes provided the basic conditions of low current density and/or low concentration are maintained. Some typical results are presented in Table 2. The main features can be summarised as follows

(i) Almost all electrolytes at (N/1000) concentration and 1mA/cm² current density produce

explosive mixtures both at the cathode and at the anode. Usually the deficit is about 10-25 percent at the cathode and more so (20-40%) at the anode. The ratio V_C/V_A has values generally in the neighbourhood of 3.

(ii) As the current density is increased, the results become more and more Faradaic, at 20-30 mA the results become almost Faradaic for most N/1000 electrolytes.

(iii) As the concentration is increased the results tend to become Faradaic and at about normal concentration the anomalous features almost disappear (vide Fig 3).

(iv) Although the behaviour tends to become Faradaic as the current and/or concentration are increased the threshold values depend upon the nature of the electrolyte.

(v) If the inter-electrode distance is increased by increasing the height of the U-tube, the anomalies tend to be more pronounced. In 5' high (i.e. 10' inter-electrode distance) U-tubes two of which we have been running for months at a stretch, the anomalies are far stronger than in a 1' high U-tube (Fig. 4).

TABLE 1. ELECTROLYSIS RESULTS OF CONDUCTIVITY H₂O vs 1(N) K₂SO₄ SOLUTION

Electrolyte	Current density mA/cm ²	Conductivity H ₂ O				1(N)K ₂ SO ₄					
		V_C/V_{FC} %	O ₂ % in V_C	V_A/V_{FA} %	H ₂ % in V_A	V_C/V_A	V_C/V_{FC} %	O ₂ % in V_C	V_A/V_{FA} %	H ₂ % in V_A	V_C/V_A
Type A (Fig. 1a) U-tube (Fig. 1c)	0.35	47	16.7	25	4.6	3.76	99.3	0.2	99	Nil	2.00
Type B (Fig. 1b)	1	92.2	30.5	33.3	50	5.54	97.5	0.15	98	Nil	2.01
"	0.35	36	31.9	16	62.5	4.5	98	Nil	99	Nil	1.98
"	0.70	64	31.2	26	42.3	4.92	97.5	Nil	98.3	Nil	1.98
"	1.00	64	28.1	34	47	3.76	98.2	0.1	98.5	Nil	1.99
"	1.23	65	29.2	33	48.5	3.94	98.5	Nil	98.8	Nil	1.99

TABLE 2. RESULTS OF ANOMALOUS ELECTROLYSIS WITH THE SALT SOLUTIONS

Electrolyte	Cell type	Current density mA/cm ²	V _C /V _{FC} %	O ₂ % in V _C	V _A /V _{FA} %	H ₂ % in V _A	V _C /V _A
K ₂ SO ₄ (0.001N)	Type A (Fig. 1a)	1	82	12	75	20	2.19
Na ₂ SO ₄ (0.001N)	Type B (Fig. 1b)	0.7	59.7	20	43.4	30	2.75
Na ₂ SO ₄ (0.001N)	U-tube (Fig. 1c)	1	87.3	24	60.4	40	2.89
Na ₂ SO ₄ (0.01N)	..	1	89.9	15	83.4	28	2.16
Na ₂ SO ₄ (0.00N)	..	10	~100	14	84.5	20.9	2.37

Fig. 3. Electrolysis results of sodium sulphate solutions at varying concentrations at 1 mA/cm² in a U-tube.

Fig. 4. Results showing the effect of inter-electrode distance in U-tubes [Soln-0.001(N) Na₂SO₄; Electrodes-Pt foil; current density-1 mA/cm²]

A—for 5' high U-tube
 B—for 1' high U-tube
 C—Results expected from Faraday's law.

(vi) The extent of the anomalies is affected by the condition of the electrode. As the surface of the latter changes in the course of an electrolysis, a good degree of reproducibility is not attained among successive runs. The

nature of electrode has a pronounced effect on the degree of anomalies as can be seen from Fig. 5. where the results obtained on replacing a platinum anode by a graphite anode have been described.

(vii) The degree of the anomalies is also dependent upon cell geometry. Among other factors affecting the degree of anomalies are temperature and stirring.

doubt the question naturally arises as to the cause of such anomalies. The following suggestions, some of which have been offered by fellow-scientists are worth our consideration.

Fig. 5. Effect of nature of the anode. [Soln—0.001(N) Na_2SO_4 ; cell—U-tube; cathode—Pt foil; current—1 mA]

A—for graphite anode
 B—for platinum anode
 C—Volume expected on the basis of Faraday's law.

The general features of non-Faradaic electrolysis can easily be demonstrated within a period of 3-5 hrs using the demonstration apparatus shown in Fig. 6. Pass a current of 5-10 mA for 3-5 hrs through a 0.001(N) electrolyte say K_2SO_4 and then note down the V_C/V_A ratio which would be found to be greater than 2. Next send a spark to the cathode gas and the anode gas when each of them will explode with a loud report and a considerable contraction in volume demonstrating the anomaly of co-liberation. Some results obtained with this apparatus are given in Table 3.

Theory

The three basic non-Faradaic features (the basic anomalies) being thus established beyond reasonable

1. *Reverse Migration of Microbubbles*: After a gas, say hydrogen is liberated, the molecules associate to form microbubbles which then receive one or more electrons from the cathode. These negatively charged microbubbles of hydrogen then migrate to the anode thus causing co-liberation at anode. By a similar process oxygen microbubbles by loss of electron to the anode form positively charged microbubbles which then migrate to the cathode.

Fig. 6 Demonstration apparatus.

A serious objection to such an idea is its failure to explain why co-liberation is almost zero in a strong solution or under high current density. Furthermore, such a reverse inter-electrode migration should re-

TABLE 3. RESULTS FROM DEMONSTRATION APPARATUS

Electrolyte	Conc. (N)	Current density mA/cm ²	Contraction on explosion,		V_C/V_A
			V_C	V_A	
K_2SO_4	0.001	1	70 - 85%	44 - 60%	3.7-6.0
K_2SO_4	0.001	5	35 - 60%	25 - 40%	2.8-4.4
K_2SO_4	0.001	10	~38%	~25%	~2.5
Na_2SO_4	0.001	10	30 - 48%	18 - 30%	2.5-3.0
KClO_4	0.001	10	~32%	~21%	~2.4
NaNO_3	0.001	10	36 - 57%	22 - 32%	2.2-3.3
Na_2SO_4	0.01	10	22 - 33%	11 - 21%	2.1-2.5
$\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$	0.017	10	27 - 46%	13 - 25%	~2.3

quire at least a few hours but co-liberation appears from the beginning of electrolysis.

2. *Formation of Charged Water*: Since water tends to get positively charged, it is conceivable that positively charged cluster of water molecules form near the anode and move towards the cathode. This is similar to space charge formation in radio valves. The movement of such water molecules is responsible for the anomalies, particularly the deficits. It might be quite possible that there may be a hitherto unsuspected migration of water molecules in both directions, say, some kind of electrolytic convection and this may somehow create the observed anomalies. However, it is difficult to see how such an idea can account for co-liberation, particularly co-liberation of hydrogen at the anode.

3. *Electronic Conduction*: It may be assumed that similar to some crystals electrolytes of low ion population conduct current both electrolytically and electronically at the same time. The electronic transport may possibly be through a relay mechanism. Thus it is conceivable that when a proton is discharged at the cathode, the OH^- ion left without partner relays its negative charge to the anode either directly or by a relay process through intermediate water molecules. This may lead to various situations creating all the complications of the basic anomalies.

According to this idea current passes through an electrolyte by both ionic and electronic mechanism. Some of these electrons cause decomposition of water near the electrodes and this is responsible for the observed co-liberation. It is implicit in such a mechanism that the total gas (hydrogen plus oxygen) liberated at the cathode may be even fifty per cent in excess of the Faradaic value V_{FC} —an eventuality which has so far not been observed. The speaker however tends to incline towards this ion-electron mechanism.

Search for other anomalies:

While working with cells of various geometry it was observed that in some cases a part of the gases tends to get liberated in the non-electrode intermediate zone (IZ). This was followed up and a number of anomalies was observed. These are listed below:

- 4) *Fourth anomaly*:
Intermediate zone (IZ) gas liberation.
- 5) *Fifth anomaly*:
Migration of inert gases like N_2 from the IZ with concurrent IZ gas liberation.
- 6) *Sixth anomaly*:
Chemical reaction in the Intermediate Zone.

The phenomenon of gas liberation in the non-electrode intermediate zone—the fourth anomaly—is most easily observed when sufficiently dilute solutions are electrolyzed in cells shown in Fig. 7 at low current

density⁵. This intermediate zone gas is a mixture of hydrogen and oxygen but not necessarily in stoichiometric proportion. Some data are cited in Table

Fig. 7. Three kinds of cell convenient for IZ gas study.

4. It has been found that such non-electrode gas liberation tends to occur in any cell where the potential gradient is lower in the intermediate zone than near the electrodes.

However, more striking is the fact that if some inert gas like nitrogen, argon, etc is already present in the intermediate zone of such cells, the IZ gas liberation is accelerated. Moreover, concurrent with this gas liberation, a considerable amount of the inert gas migrates out of the IZ to the electrodes. This feature⁶ which we refer to as fifth anomaly is most strikingly shown with barrel-type cells (Fig. 7c). Some typical results are shown in Fig. 8.

TABLE 4. RESULTS ON 'FOURTH ANOMALY' WITH 0.001(N) Na_2SO_4 SOLUTION IN E-TYPE CELLS AT 1 mA

V_{FC} (ml)	V_C (ml)	V_A (ml)	V_{IZ} (ml)	Composition of IZ gas	
				O_2	H_2
71.5	57.8	26.2	3.4	37%	63%

Having observed the occurrence of the above two peculiar phenomena in the non-electrode intermediate zone, one is left with the impression that IZ is likely

Fig. 8. Results showing the fifth anomaly : Transport of N₂. [Current—1 mA, Electrolyte—0.001(N) Na₂SO₄; Cell : Barrel type (Fig. 7c); Initial "IZ" content —50 ml N₂]

to be a zone of chemical reactivity. To test this conjecture, small quantities of some organic materials like benzene, chlorobenzene, nitrobenzene, aniline, etc were put in the intermediate zone and electrolysis continued under low electrolyte concentration and low current density condition. The experiment brings out another novel result. It has been observed that on continuing electrolysis, the solution gets darkened and this darkening starts from the IZ and then spreads slowly usually towards the anode. The organic materials get transformed into a complex mixture which appears to contain polyphenols. This observation indicates that the intermediate zone is a seat of intense chemical activity—the sixth anomaly⁷.

Boundary formation during electrolysis :

Another anomalous behaviour which is a novel observation made by the speaker viz. formation of sharp boundaries on electrolysis^{8,9}. This behaviour is novel in the sense that the passage of electric current here creates order in a system, a behaviour which is very unusual and unexpected considering the general disruptive action of current. The simplest of such

boundary formation is seen by electrolysing a neutral dye solution in a U-tube. A sharp boundary gradually forms right near the cathode bend and continues to remain stationary thereafter irrespective of whether the dye is a cationic or an-anionic one (B₁ in Fig. 9). Such boundary forms not only in a U-tube but also in a horizontal tube but not in a vertical tube. The most striking behaviour however is shown if the electrolysis is conducted in a W-tube, a double-bent U-tube (Fig. 10). Two sharp boundaries generally form dividing the solution into three zones, a coloured zone CB₁ of pH ~ 11, a colourless zone B₁B₂ of more or less neutral pH and another coloured zone B₂A of pH ~ 3. The two boundaries appear to form *ab initio* at the place where they become eventually visible and do not migrate with the current. This behaviour is shown not only by many dye solutions but also by many inorganic salts for example a dichromate solution even at sufficiently high concentration and current strength⁹.

Although the observation that the central zone in a W-tube gets highly depleted of ions is highly anomalous and is evidently an anti-Hittorf phenomenon, it is found to be a general feature of electro-

Fig. 9. U-tube.

Fig. 10. W-tube.

lysis in a W-tube type cells. The phenomenon of such double boundary formation being of extensive occurrence, the technique may be explored for practical applications like desalination of brackish water and preparation of caustic alkali without using costly mercury or membranes.

Fig. 11. Some typical behaviour resulting from electrolysis in W-tubes.

Formation of such columns of solutions separated by sharp boundaries on electrolysis is also observed in alcoholic media. However with many dyes, the behaviour becomes more interesting and complex. Sometimes more than two boundaries appear, and when two such boundaries are very near to each other, the inter-boundary region appears like a band which is often colourless. Some typical behaviour is shown in Fig.11. Since it is thus demonstrated that passage of electric current may be accompanied by structure

formation, it is conceivable that the structure formation responsible for creation of life in the primordial earth may have been caused by passage of electricity.

7. Conclusion

The question naturally arises "Is Faraday's law violated?" The string of facts discussed as above undoubtedly does not fall in the pattern of Faraday's law and classical concepts of electrochemical migration. Nevertheless, it is always possible to surmise that the law is valid for the primary process (which need not be a typical chemical reaction but may embrace even a mere electronic transaction with the electrode) and any observed departure is due to subsequent secondary reactions. The situation is somewhat similar to the famous Einstein's law of photochemical equivalence. By such a circumvention Faraday's law may probably be saved but only at the expense of its great predictive value for which it is held in such high esteem. By such a revision the law immediately becomes an undependable guide to what to expect from an electrochemical experiment. As science can ill afford to ignore facts, we are faced with the dilemma of either circumscribing the zone of validity of Faraday's law or revising it to a status of chemical impotence where it becomes a mere paraphrasing of a physical fact in a pseudochemical language. The choice between these two courses depends on the individual taste. But the compulsive logic of facts leads to the certain conclusion that there exists a vast field in electrolysis where many novel unexpected things occur and this needs fresh thinking and critical experimentation. The speaker invites you all to this highly rewarding task.

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